

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KILAMA****FIRST NAME: FELIX DOUGLAS****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 00%

The author used the following software: MS Office Standard 2010 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Comprehending applied and pure research concepts is essential to a scholar in developing a framework guiding a study, formulating a testable hypothesis or research problem, and designing an appropriate method of collecting and analyzing data. Applied research
 - Seeks to improve the understanding of a community of researchers. It addresses a conceptual problem that may have little practical consequences.
 - Can lead to developing policies, strategies, processes, products, and technologies to address the direct impacts of problems on people's lives.¹**

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 9th ed. (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 42.

- It gathers information or knowledge about a problem, but its conclusion may have yet to have immediate real-world use.
 - Intends to generate new ideas, theories, or principles that can be useful later and conducted without a specific practical application.
2. The main reason for a literature review is more than just describing previous research related to my topic or providing a context for my dissertation research. It analyzes and synthesizes previous studies about my research topic to make a case for my research problem. Synthesis, therefore
- Involves reviewing, describing, summarizing, and evaluating essential scholarly works and other sources relevant to my topic.
 - State the gaps in the works of other scholars or researchers. Describes what still needs to be studied or investigated.
 - Goes beyond critique to determine the relationships, patterns, or trends among sources. It involves identification, comparing, and contrasting shared themes or concepts and extracting content from different sources to create an original text in a new structure.²**
 - Presents a summary of literature assessed during research, including those with little or no connection between or among them.
3. A research problem is a specific issue, contradiction, challenge, or gap in knowledge that a study seeks to address. A conceptual problem

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation, A Road Map from the Beginning to the End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 387.

- Explain the causes of the issues and propose feasible or tangible solutions.
 - Can be caused by some conditions in the world that negatively affect us in terms of time, lives or limbs, money, security, opportunity, and other costs.
 - Its solution can be eliminating or mitigating the conditions creating it.
 - Arises from gaps in our understanding of something in the world that we ought to know. Therefore, we want to bridge these gaps by answering questions that help us understand the world better.**³
4. Limitations of the study are those characteristics of research designs or methodology that impacted or influenced the interpretation of the findings from my research. On the other hand, delimitations are
- The shortcomings of my study based on practical or theoretical constraints that I faced during my study.
 - Limitations that I consciously set as a researcher. They are anticipated constraints in the interpretation of the findings of the dissertation research.**⁴
 - Limitations regarding transferability, applications to practice, and utility of findings result from how I chose to design the study.
 - Unforeseen factors that may limit or restrict the interpretation of data in my study.
5. The three below belong to the Turabian style of reference list except

³ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 41.

⁴ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 49.

- Kinder, Donald R., and Allison Dale-Riddle. 2012. *The End of Race? Obama, 2008, and Racial Politics in America*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
 - Mukherjee, Ankhi. *What Is a Classic? Postcolonial Rewriting and Invention of the Canon*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press, 2013.⁵**
 - Jitrik, Noé. 2005. *The Noé Jitrik Reader: Selected Essays on Latin American Literature*. Edited by Daniel Balderston. Translated by Susan E. Benner. Durham, NC: Duke University Press.
 - Centinel [pseud.]. 1981. "Letters." In *The Complete Anti-Federalist*, edited by Herbert J. Storing. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
6. Qualitative research involves collecting data on participants' behaviors, experiences, and perceptions and analyzing and interpreting such data. While quantitative research design
- Asks open-ended questions and answers the how and whys.
 - Can explain processes and patterns of human behaviors that can be difficult to quantify.
 - Is applied to describe current conditions, investigate relationships, and study cause-effect phenomena.⁶**
 - It is often linear and deals with words and meaning.

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 288.

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation, A Road Map from the Beginning to the End*, 135.

7. To avoid plagiarism, one has to cite the author or source properly. One can use in-text citations and either quote the author's exact words or paraphrase them. Parenthetical citations according to Turabian style should include
- Author's name, publication date, and relevant page number (s).**⁷
 - A superscript number follows the author's last name.
 - The author's last name and the year of publication.
 - A page number follows the author's last name.
8. Each part of the structure of an essay must flow smoothly into the next one, giving the text an easy transition from one part to another. The structure of the essay should be in this format
- Abstract, statement of the problems, hypothesis, and conclusion.
 - Introduction, statement of purpose, research question, research design, and recommendations.
 - Introduction, body, and conclusion.**⁸
 - Table of contents, introduction, literature review, methodology, and conclusion.
9. In the European Commission, one has to follow specific rules when drafting or translating outgoing letters. If you use "Dear Sir/Madam" to open the letter, you should close it with "Yours faithfully." Suppose you start by stating the name of the

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 240.

⁸ Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1* (Euclid University, 2021), 10.

person the letter addresses, such as "Dear Mr/Ms/Dr. Freeman", then you have to close with

- Yours in truly
- Yours sincerely**⁹
- Yours respectfully
- Best regards

10. Whether you are a senior researcher or a beginner, you can learn much from the feedback of meticulous readers. There are two kinds of feedback that you can get from such readers, and these are

- Descriptive and no descriptive feedback.
- Coaching and Guidance.
- Advice and data.**¹⁰
- Evaluative and summative.

⁹ European Commission, "European Commission English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission" (European Commission, 2021), 62, https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 217.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.